

GEOLOGICAL RISK MANAGEMENT PROCESS AND ITS PARTICULARITIES FOR A URANIUM SITE - CASE STUDY

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ABSTRACT. Anthropogenic radioactive pollution of the environment resulting from the research and exploitation of uranium resources is a topical issue for the scientific community because it represents a threat to people's health conditions and has a highly negative impact on the environment. The sources of radioactive pollution are due to the presence of low-level radioactive tailings and poor ore dumps resulting from the exploration and exploitation of uranium ore deposits. Uranium under the action of environmental factors can reach the groundwater, the river network, and the food chain, respectively. The contaminated food and water may cause diseases and even cancer. An important role in the pollution spreading is played by geological phenomena, the most important being landslides. Thus arises the need for geological risk management. The present study aims to implement a geological risk management system through methods of assessment, monitoring, and prediction of geological risk for a chosen uranium site. The waste rock and water samples analysis pointed out the radioactive contamination risk. The simulated scenarios in the area exposed to subsidence phenomena showed the activity of increasing the concentration of radioactive waste in the hydrographic system's groundwater in the studied site, in a time interval of 4120 days (11.29 years): it rapidly increased in the first 1000 days (from 0.0 to 0.0033), after which it decreased in intensity until day 2500 (from 0.0033 to 0.0048), and it is supposed to stagnate after day 2500 until day 4120 when the simulation ended. The results emphasised the radioactive contamination spreading risk in the case when the subsidence phenomenon takes place.

Keywords: geological risk, uranium mining site, landslides, monitoring of geological parameters

Introduction

Anthropogenic radioactive sources that have occurred in the environment due to uranium resources' research and exploitation were inappropriately managed during the time. The interaction between existing sources of radioactive pollution on sites or in underground mining works and natural phenomena generating geological risk can particularly amplify the destructive effects on communities and natural habitats, which can persist in the very long term; remedial measures are currently very expensive and unfeasible.

In this context, the geological risk management process can be an effective method of preventing radioactive pollution of the environment.

The implementation of modern methodologies used internationally in the forecast of landslides that occur on tailing dumps in the uranium mining sites may result in reducing the geological and radiological risk (Mejía-Navarro, 1994; INCDMRR, 2006-2009). Getting the most accurate prediction results makes it possible to reduce the vulnerability degree of receptors in the influence area.

The chosen area as a case study in this paper is the Avram Iancu uranium mining site in the Arieşului Mic basin, Alba County.

In this study, determinations of the gamma dose on the dumps in the chosen site were used to measure the radioactive contamination.

Chemical analysis of samples taken from rocks deposited on the dump, soils, and waters, determinations of Rn concentrations on the dumps' surface and at the entrance of accessible galleries; besides performing laboratory tests to determine radioactive elements were also applied.

Methods and equipment

Landslide forecasting is achieved through different types of approaches: deterministic, direct, indirect, statistical, and GIS (Van Westen, 2004):

- deterministic methods are based on the calculation of the stability factor;
- direct methods aim at positioning landslides on maps and making landslide distribution maps;
- indirect methods are based on the analysis of the conditions of occurrence (slope, lithological, land use) of landslides;
- statistical and GIS methods are used to process and interpret data obtained by direct and indirect methods (Ayalew, 2005).

Gamma radiation is emitted by radionuclides contained in waste rock deposited in dumps or poor ore deposits (Baeza and Corominas, 2001).

Radon 222 is a radioactive gas found on the surface of uranium-poor tailings or ore deposits and has a high degree of risk and is associated with 15% of lung cancer cases.

Zajzon and co-authors (2015) pointed out the presence of heavy metals in the studied area.

Infiltration from tailings dumps can contaminate surface water and groundwater with Radium 226, but also with other substances occurring in the uranium deposit (heavy metals, arsenic, pyrite) (Zajzon et al., 2015).

The determination of gamma radiation in the field was performed with the FAGFH40F2 radiometer, with a sensitivity of 0.01 μ Sv / h.

The determination of uranium, radium, thorium, and cesium in soil and sediment samples was performed in parallel by

gamma spectrometry, with the four-channel analyser type NP 424 and with the multichannel analyser type ORTEC-2000 with Ge Hyper-pure detector.

Results and discussions

Characterisation of the studied mining site

The Băița-Avram Iancu exploitation zone is delimited to the north (Figure 1) by the confluence of the waters between Valea Calului and Crișul Băița; to the south by the confluence of the waters between Valea Leucii and Piatra Aradului; to the east by the Bihor Peak and by the springs of Arieș Mic and by the left slope of Arieș; to the west by Tăul Mare Peak and by the springs of Dedeșului brook and Dibarz brook. From a territorial

administrative point of view, the exploitation site is located at the border between Bihor, Alba, and Arad counties, but it belongs to Bihor County.

In the Bihor mining site (Băița, Avram Iancu) which occupies an area of 50 km², there is a multitude of mineralisations with different genesis from U and Mo, W, Bi, Ni, Co, Pb, Cu, Ag, Zn, B (Figure 2) (Zajzon *et al.*, 2015.)

Fig. 1. Mining site location and access roads (adapted from INCDMRR report)

Fig. 2. Schematic geological section through the Avram Iancu deposit (adapted from Geology studies and research)

Tailing dumps in the Avram Iancu site (Arieşului Mic basin - sector North) (Figure 3), where G stands for gallery, are as follows:

- Dump of G X North: made up of waste rocks dominated by quartz-feldspar shales.
- Dump of G XX: it consists of the tailings from the underground penetration works on the surface of the XX horizon, now it is naturally restored from an ecological point of view.
- Dump of G XII gallery: consists of waste rocks dominated by quartz-feldspar shales and chlorite shales.
- Dump G I Arieş: located on the right slope of the Arieşului Mic valley at approximately 35 m from the valley level, and the dump extends on the slope from the elevation +1165 m to the elevation +1133 m near the Arieş Mic valley.
- Dump of G Arieş: The entrance of the gallery is located on the right bank of the Arieş Mic Valley, about 1.5 m above its riverbed.
- Dump of G VI Arieş: Located on the right side of the Arieş Mic Valley, it occupies an area of about 950 m² and it is the result of the excavation of gallery VI located at an altitude of +1140 m.
- Dump of G XI Vechi şi Nou: The tailings from the opening of the old XI gallery (elevation +1120 m) were deposited in the bed of the Arieş Mic stream, respectively on either side of the gallery. The base of the gallery is about 1 m higher than the bed of Arieşului Mic.

- Dump of the G XIII Aries: The gallery started from the surface at an altitude of +1121 m; it is located on the right slope of the Arieş Mic Valley.
- Dump of the G XVI Bis: The dump has a large size occupying an area of 15,500 m² and it was used to store the tailings resulting from the opening and preparation of the ore bodies.

Obtained results

Within the Avram Iancu mining site, the following research was carried out: field measurement of the gamma flow dose on dumps; sampling of rocks deposited on the dump, soils, and waters; determination of Rn concentrations on the surface of dumps and at the entrance of accessible galleries; laboratory analyses for the determination of radioactive elements (U, Ra, Rn).

The data obtained were displayed in Tables 1 and 2 or were subsequently represented in two dimensions as distributions of gamma parameters on the measured area (Figure 4).

The data displayed in Table 1 pointed out that the highest content of U and Ra was recorded in the leakage from G XII, namely, 0.105 mg/L and 0.070 Bq/L, respectively. Therefore, the radioactive contamination risk is high.

Fig. 3. Location of tailings dumps in the area of the Avram Iancu mining site - North

Table 1. Mining with seepage in the receiver (Arieșul Mic)

No.	Name of the work	Flow (L/s)	Minimum flow of the receiver at the point of emergence (L/s) P = 95%	Content in items radioactive		Spill into the environment (stream)
				U (mg/L)	Ra (Bq/L)	
1	G. XII	1.5	15.6	0.105	0.070	Arieșul Mic
2	G. Arieș	0.04	15.6	0.008	0.009	Arieșul Mic
3	G. XI Vechi Arieș	3	17	0.075	0.058	Arieșul Mic
	MAC* drinking water according to STAS** 1342/91			0.021	0.088	

*MAC= maximum admitted concentration and **STAS = Romanian standard that regulates U and Ra content in drink water in Romania

The data from Table 2 showed that dump G VI has the highest content of uranium and radium (850 g/t and 11.86 Bq/t, respectively) confirming the radioactive contamination as well.

The 3D model database includes geological maps and sections, data from geotechnical drilling, vector information, numerical models, hydrogeological data, and temporal information as shown in Figure 5.

All the information is extremely useful to model the northern sector of the Avram Iancu mining site.

The next steps required to build the three-dimensional model for the Avram Iancu mining site - the northern sector were (Figures 6 and 7): obtaining the digital terrain model; overlapping external elements on the digital surface model: tailings dumps, hydrographic network (Arieșul Mic stream),

Table 2. Radiometric measurements and radionuclides determination on dumps

Name / location/ elevation	Surface (m ²)	Maximum content in radioactive elements		Maximum gamma dose rate (μSv/h)	The value of the maximum concentration of Rn (Bq/m ³)	Stored material	Location relative to watercourses	Surface with gamma dose rate values > 0,3μSv/h* (m ²)
		U (g/t)	Ra (Bq/g)					
Dump G. X North 1181 m	850	10	0.05	0.03	35	Crystalline shales from the Biharia series	On the right slope of the Arieșului Mic valley	-
Dump GXII East 1153 m	1800	4	0.03	0.45	40			10
Dump G.I 1164 m	1200	70	0.7	0.65	75			70
Dump GVI 1140 m	950	850	11.86	1.9	370			100
Dump G. Arieș 1134 m	160	15	0.047	0.25	25		Near the Arieșului Mic valley	-
Dump G.XI Nou 1120 m	1955	12	0.1	0.55	50		On the right slope of the Arieșului Mic valley	75
Dump GXIII 1121 m	7500	36	0.23	0.28	38			-
Dump GXVI bis 1130 m	15550	150	1.25	1.02	145	2100		

*Maximum admitted limit for gamma radiation dose rate in ecological reconstruction

Fig. 4. Distribution of the gamma dose on the main dumps of the Avram Iancu mining site

Fig. 5. Integration of geospatial information into the 3D model database

closure works at the surface (gabion walls, closing plates for open wells); realisation of the network of underground mining works (directional, transversal galleries, open wells and blind wells, sloping planes); reconstitution of mineralised bodies that have been exploited; realisation of the 3D model of the geological structure including the known tectonic elements (Chung and Fabbri, 2002). Specialised software was used in the steps listed above: Global Mapper, AutoCad, QuickSurf, GoCAD, Interdex, GoogleSketchup, and ArcGis.

Fig. 6. The stages of building the digital surface model

Fig. 7. Methodology for processing the structure of mining works in the Avram lancu site

Spatial representations required for the design of the monitoring network

The technique of SAR interferometry (InSAR) is known for the speed and accuracy of collecting topographic data. Synthetic Aperture Radar (SAR) images contain both the amplitude and the phase of return signals from the Earth's surface.

Through a special algorithm and manual editing, the landscape elements are removed, and the digital terrain model is generated.

Due to the non-existence of topographic plans in electronic format, the situation plans of the site at a scale of 1: 2000 were used. This plan was scanned to an appropriate resolution so as not to lose important details, and the resulting file was uploaded to Global Mapper software version 9 and georeferenced after the grid on the Stereo 70 projection system.

The 10 m curves were digitised and assigned the corresponding elevation value of the elevation and then used to check and correct the elevations. Also, a capture of spatial coordinates was made on a network with a resolution of 10 m in the site area (Figure 8) by using a specialised extension under ArcGis that allows obtaining in KML format a series of coordinates in geographical format from the Google Earth.

Once the database is obtained by inventory, thus knowing the situation at a given time, we move on to the study of susceptibility, i.e., to the definition of areas that may be prone to landslides (areas with subunit safety factors).

Fig. 8. The use of classical and satellite cartographic material for the digital model of the terrain in the northern area of the former Avram lancu uranium mine

The steps that were taken to determine the safety index in the study area were: to convert the original map from DEM to a raster format (Figure 9); raster maps with flow directions and slopes drawing (Figure 10); calculate the specific surface of the receiving basin (Figure 11); calculation of the stability index and the humidity index (Figure 12) and representation of the slope chart and the specific reception area, as well as the distribution of stability indices by stability categories (Figures 13, and 14).

Fig. 9. Raster map processed for abnormal areas with negative relief

Fig. 13. Saturation index map

Fig. 10. Raster map with flow directions

Fig. 14. Stability index map

Fig. 11. Slope map

Fig. 12. Map of areas contributing to landslides

Due to the increased permeability of the material in the area of the sinking bed (Figure 15) and due to the stretching and compression, this can be a path of draining rainwater or torrential water loaded with radioactive contaminants due to washing waste dumps or poor ore deposits that have not been completely evacuated. Thus, the integrated GIS system can point out, for different profiles chosen automatically or by the user, the exceeding of some alert thresholds regarding the evolution of certain parameters of the subsidence.

The processing performed with the help of the subsidence module, the two- and three-dimensional graphical representations (Figures 16 and 17), and the dynamic evolutions through the integrated GIS system can be used to predict this geohazard phenomenon and the drawing of thematic risk maps to be used in estimating vulnerability to environmental factors and habitats. The obtained results can show the areas exposed to risk, areas that can amplify the radioactive contamination of the environment by leaching into the local hydrographic system or in the underground waters of some waste with radioactive loading (Figures 18 and 19).

In the contamination source's area, the drilling was located to monitor the source's concentration and downstream were located another 5 boreholes for monitoring the concentrations of U and the piezometric level.

Figure 18 shows the area exposed to subsidence phenomena and Figure 19 the activity of increasing the concentration of radioactive waste in the hydrographic system's groundwater in the studied site, in a time interval of 4120 days (11.29 years):

Fig. 15. 3D representation of the sinking bed (mining subsidence) for the monitored location

Fig. 16. Discretisation of the deposit in calculation blocks for calculating the subsidence

Fig. 17. Horizontal deformation dependence on the time variation for a landmark in the mining subsidence monitoring network

Fig. 18. Areas exposed to subsidence phenomena in the site Avram Iancu - Ariesul Mic basin

Fig. 19. Simulation of U radionuclide dispersion in groundwater (source of continuous contamination, steady flow)

It has an accelerated increase in the first 1000 days (from 0.0 to 0.0033), after which it decreases in intensity until day 2500 (from 0.0033 to 0.0048), and it will stagnate after day 2500 until day 4120 when the simulation ended.

With some control data of the contents of the boreholes or even of the wells, it is possible to calibrate the concentration of the contaminant to have some information that is somewhat relevant for the proposal of a monitoring network.

Drawing hazard maps when slipping

Two methods were considered, namely statistical analysis

and deterministic method with modelling of local geological, hydrogeological, and seismic conditions (Paudits, 2002, Remongo, 2005, Thywisen, 2006).

The statistical method for the execution of slip hazard maps is based on quantitatively determined weighted values. With the help of these maps, different scenarios related to the stochastic evolution of the parameters with an impact on the triggering of geohazard phenomena: hydrogeological, geological, and seismic parameters (Figure 20).

Fig. 20. Scenarios related to the stochastic evolution of the parameters with impact on the onset of geohazard phenomena

The steps followed in the evaluation of the slip hazard were: intercorrelation of the slip maps with the parameter maps; for each category (e.g. lithological units, slope class) the weighted value is calculated (the ratio between the natural log of the slip density on the respective class and the slip density for the whole map - Figure 21): slips will be less than a

normal threshold value, and weighted values will be positive when the slip density is higher than the threshold value, by algebraically summing (or by other defined criteria) the weighted maps.

Fig. 21. Parametric and occurrence maps used in hazard assessment

Conclusions

The implementation of modern methodologies in the forecast of landslides that occur in the dumps in the uranium mining sites can result in a decrease in geological and radiological risk. Making predictions as accurate as possible can decrease the degree of vulnerability of the receptors in the influence area.

The need to represent and analyse large informational volumes of spatial (georeferenced) and non-spatial data on the short and long-term assessment of the risk induced on the environment and implicitly on human communities by former uranium mining, requires the use of software applications GIS. Hazard (landslide, subsidence, flood, earthquake, contamination) mapping techniques are implemented through separate modules or procedures within the GIS geological risk management platform and are based on stochastic or deterministic methods.

With the help of these maps, different scenarios related to the stochastic evolution of the parameters with an impact on the onset of geohazard phenomena can be made later, to reduce or even eliminate the negative effects induced on the environment or the human community by uranium sites.

The simulated scenarios in the area exposed to subsidence phenomena showed the activity of increasing the concentration of radioactive waste in the hydrographic system's groundwater in the studied site, in a time interval of 4120 days (11.29 years): it rapidly increased in the first 1000 days (from 0.0 to 0.0033), after which it decreased in intensity until day 2500 (from 0.0033 to 0.0048), and it is supposed to stagnate after day 2500 until day 4120 when the simulation ended. The results pointed at the radioactive contamination spreading risk in the case when the subsidence incident takes place.

Acknowledgments

The present research was financed by the Ministry of Research, Innovation, and Digitalisation, Core Programme, Contract no. 43N/2019.

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